

Exploring Talent Leadership in Higher Education Institutions: A Comprehensive Analysis

Doreen Morukhu and Tracy Nyatheli

Department of Human Resource Management and Labour Relations, University of Venda, South Africa

This study examines the role of talent leadership in developing high-potential academics within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in South Africa. The research aims to understand various aspects, including the definition of high-potential academics, the role of educational leaders in talent management, factors hindering the development of high-potential academics and strategies for their development. Using a Social Constructivist paradigm, the study explores subjective meanings and interactions to understand participants' perspectives. It also integrates human resource theories like Herzberg's motivation theory and Maslow's hierarchy of needs to find solutions. Ten academics out of a population of 850 were interviewed, and data analysis was conducted using Atlas-ti (Version 8.0) to identify themes and categories that aligned with the research objectives. The findings highlight the critical role of talent leadership in developing high-potential academics. Factors such as funding for publications and conferences, effective communication, work-life balance, skills development and recognition are crucial for maintaining academic satisfaction. The study recommends that Human Resource Management prioritize selecting competent leaders, fostering communication dynamics, adopting emerging innovations, funding projects, creating roles, and building a supportive organisational culture to support the development of high-potential academics in HEIs in South Africa.

Keywords: Academic satisfaction, high potential academics, higher education institutions

This study focused on the role of talent leadership in developing high-potential academics. The fundamentals of achieving growth in organisations or institutions rely on the ability of management to discover high-potential talents (Festing & Shafer, 2014:263). However, high-potential talents need to be groomed to stay competitive. The study of Collings (2014:302) affirms that talent management refers to the systematic identification, development, retention and deployment of employees with high potential who will be of great value to an organisation/institution. It encompasses the individual and organisational development concerning a changing and complex operating environment.

In the past decades, there has been a great transformation in the human resource practices amongst Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) due to changes in technology, innovations and the economic/business environment (Van Zyl et al., 2017:2). It is in the capacity of talent management to create and maintain a supportive and people-oriented organisation culture. According to Odierno (2015:10), it is not adequate to only recruit potential academics. They are supposed to be engaged, developed and rewarded suitably, viewed as the responsibility of talent leadership. Talent leadership is viewed as a mobile workforce empowered to change the

organisation (Church et al., 2015:17).

The attraction, development, management and retention of talent are essential drivers of success, which is the core responsibility of talent leadership. Talent leadership in Institutions in South Africa enables leaders to discover talents, grow their abilities and pursue their interests to attain the institution's objectives. This study examined the roles of talent leadership in developing high-potential academics in Higher Learning Institutions. Also, focus was placed on talent leaders' roles in keeping the Higher Education Institutions.

Background

The challenge of retaining high-potential academics in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in South Africa is multifaceted, with implications for delivering quality education and maintaining institutional competitiveness (Odierno, 2015; Geber, 2009; Arris et al., 2013). Research suggests that these challenges contribute to low morale among academics, leading to high turnover rates that hinder the achievement of institutional objectives (Silzer & Dowell, 2009). However, there exists a notable gap in scholarly research explicitly focusing on academic talent leadership and development within the South African context, with most studies concentrating on training and development rather than on leadership practices (Boshard & Louw, 2011). Recognising the importance of nurturing future leaders from within, many HEIs in South Africa have initiated talent leadership and management programmes to address these challenges and reduce job turnover rates (Cook, 2012).

In exploring the role of talent leadership in developing high-potential academics, the study aims to achieve several crucial objectives for understanding and addressing the identified issues. Firstly, the study seeks to understand how high-potential academics are identified within HEIs. This objective is rooted in recognising the importance of talent identification as a foundational step in talent management processes (Tansley, 2011; Tyagi et al., 2017). Secondly,

Author Note

Doreen Morukhu, Department of Human Resource Management and Labour Relations, University of Venda, South Africa
Tracy Nyatheli, Department of Human Resources Management and Labour Relations, University of Venda, South Africa
E-mail: tracy.nyatheli@univen.ac.za

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Doreen Morukhu, Department of Human Resource Management and Labour Relations, University of Venda, South Africa
E-mail: doreen.morukhu@univen.ac.za

it aims to investigate the competencies and capabilities that high-potential academics should possess. This objective aligns with theories such as Maslow's hierarchy of needs, which emphasises the importance of self-actualisation and personal growth in academic development (Maslow, 1943). Additionally, insights from Scott et al. (2013) highlight the role of competencies in leadership development.

Thirdly, the study intends to identify the role of higher educational leaders in talent management within HEIs in South Africa. These objective underscores leadership's pivotal role in identifying and developing high-potential employees (Muteswa, 2016; Gallo, 2015). Furthermore, the study aims to establish the competencies that leaders should possess to effectively develop high-potential academics. Drawing from the literature on leadership development programmes, this objective emphasises the importance of leadership competencies such as communication, decision-making, and coaching (Piip, 2015; Gallo, 2015).

Moreover, the study seeks to describe the mechanisms leaders can employ to foster job satisfaction and maintain high potential academic happiness in the workplace. This objective is supported by theories such as Herzberg's motivation and hygiene theory, which highlight the importance of addressing extrinsic and intrinsic factors to promote job satisfaction (Herzberg et al., 2008). Additionally, the study aims to investigate the factors that may constrain leaders in their efforts to develop high-potential academics within HEIs. This objective draws from research on talent management practices, identifying barriers such as organisational culture, resource constraints and ineffective communication strategies (Campbell & Hirsh, 2013; Stahl et al., 2012).

The study endeavours to identify the necessary support mechanisms that higher education institutions must provide to facilitate leaders in developing high-potential academics. This objective is informed by studies emphasising the importance of organisational support and resource allocation in talent management and leadership development initiatives (Krugel, 2014; McDonnell et al., 2017). Therefore, by addressing these objectives, the study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on talent management and leadership in academia, providing actionable recommendations for improving talent leadership practices in HEIs in South Africa.

Literature Review (Theories and Empirical Review)

The theoretical background of talent management in this study is firmly rooted in various management theories, which have been developed to improve talent retention and enhance organisational performance within higher education institutions (HEIs) (Creswell, 2014). As a human resources management component, talent management integrates theories aimed at maximising employee potential and fostering retention (Bernard, 2012).

One prominent theory discussed is Herzberg's motivation and hygiene theory, which delineates hygiene factors and motivators, emphasising their impact on job satisfaction and dissatisfaction (Lundberg et al., 2008; Bernard, 2012). According to Herzberg, hygiene factors, such as working conditions and supervision, address basic needs but do not necessarily motivate employees. In contrast, motivators, like recognition and advancement, stimulate satisfaction and productivity (Lundberg et al., 2008).

Maslow's hierarchy of needs is also prominent in the theoretical framework, categorising human needs into physiological, safety, belongingness, esteem and self-actualisation levels (Muteswa & Ortlep, 2014). This theory suggests that meeting these needs can motivate individuals and promote higher performance levels (Taormina & Gao, 2013). Maslow's hierarchy underscores the importance of addressing basic and higher-order needs to facilitate employee engagement and retention (Bernard, 2012).

Besides, the Expectancy theory proposed by V.H. Vroom elucidates the relationship between effort, performance, and outcomes, emphasising the role of perceived rewards in motivating employees (Lunenburg, 2011). This theory posits that individuals are motivated to exert effort if they believe it will lead to desirable outcomes (Bernard, 2012). Expectancy theory underscores the importance of aligning organisational rewards with individual efforts to enhance motivation and retention (Lunenburg, 2011).

Lastly, Equity theory, developed by Adam John Stacey, highlights the importance of fairness in the workplace, particularly regarding the balance between employee inputs and outputs (Lunenburg, 2012). This theory posits that employees compare their input-output ratio with that of others, and inequity can lead to dissatisfaction and reduced motivation (Bernard, 2012). Equity theory underscores the significance of fair treatment and equitable rewards in promoting employee retention and organisational commitment (Lunenburg, 2012).

Moving over to the empirical management processes, talent management is fundamental to any organisation's survival, sustenance, competence, business relevance and success. The talent management process is broad and long, encompassing recruitment, selection and performance (Rao, 2017). Recruitment involves assessing, evaluating and eventually hiring employees into an organisation (Bersin, 2006). However, recruitment challenges, particularly attracting and retaining talented employees, are significant. Hughes and Rog (2008) emphasised that these challenges are particularly crucial in high-labour-intensive industries like tourism and hospitality, where customer service expectations are high.

They identified factors contributing to recruitment challenges, including emotional labour requirements, lack of job security, lack of promotion opportunities, low status of specific jobs and poor working conditions. Effective recruitment models involve establishing recruitment objectives, developing a strategy, carrying out recruitment activities and evaluating results. Selection, a critical aspect of the talent management process, involves various methods tailored to specific job types, such as application forms, interviews, references, assessment centres, formal tests and final selection (2015). These methods are subjective and strategic, fitting some organisations more than others.

Performance is crucial to any organisation, relating to achieving its set objectives and goals (Muatafa, 2013). It involves the contributions of individuals, employees or teams toward achieving strategic goals, encompassing outcomes achieved (Woyessa, 2015). Performance impacts an organisation in three dimensions: Being, Doing and Relating. 'Being' concerns the competencies of the employee affecting performance, 'Doing' emphasises the employee's activities impacting the organisation and 'Relating' involves relationships among members of the organisation. Performance is a combination of human activities and factors in the workplace toward

achieving organisational goals, often measured in terms of output. Mustafa (2013) defines performance as an employee's contributions that benefit the organisation economically and are not easily duplicated by competitors. Effective performance management links individual and team activities with organisational goals, values, and cultural practices (Woyessa, 2015). Sustaining performance requires training, communication and proper supervision, which are concepts of Human Resource Management used to identify, measure, and develop individual performance aligned with organisational goals.

Method and Research Design

This study adopts a social constructivist paradigm, aligning with the belief that individuals construct subjective meanings of their experiences. Through this lens, the study aims to understand the role of talent leadership in developing high-potential academics by focusing on the perspectives of academic staff and their cultural contexts (Creswell, 2014). A qualitative research design was chosen to allow for an in-depth exploration of the phenomenon under investigation. An exploratory approach was deemed suitable due to the limited literature on talent leadership in academia. The study population consisted of 850 academics from various faculties, with a purposive sampling method employed to select 10 participants representing diverse perspectives.

Data collection primarily involved face-to-face interviews with the selected academic staff, providing rich, detailed insights. Measures were taken to ensure the validity and reliability of the data collected. Construct validity was ensured by aligning interview questions with existing literature, while confirmability and credibility were achieved through thorough documentation and participant checks. Reliability was maintained through consultation with a statistician to validate the interview questions.

Data analysis was conducted using Atlas-ti software, employing thematic analysis to identify key themes and patterns within the collected data. Ethical considerations were diligently observed throughout the study, including voluntary participation, protection against harm, confidentiality, and accurate reporting of participant responses.

Results and Discussion

The discussion of the results of this research study offers valuable insights into the role of talent leadership in developing high-potential academics within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in South Africa. The findings, organised according to the research objectives, provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with talent management in academia.

The study's participants articulated a nuanced understanding of high-potential academics, emphasising qualities such as integrity, teaching proficiency and research excellence. These findings resonate with scholarly literature, identifying high-potential academics as individuals with aspirations for leadership roles and a commitment to knowledge dissemination (Allen, Bryant, & Vardaman, 2010; Hausknecht et al., 2009). Additionally, participants highlighted the importance of competencies such as critical thinking and mentoring ability, aligning with existing research on the attributes of successful academics (Hayashi & Dolan, 2013).

Participants underscored the pivotal role of leaders in talent

management within HEIs, emphasising tasks such as talent identification, strategic leadership and talent nurturing. These findings corroborate existing literature emphasising the importance of leadership in talent development and institutional growth (Schiemann, 2013; Liden et al., 2014). Effective leadership in talent management is essential for creating a conducive environment that fosters academic excellence and organisational success (Allen, Bryant & Vardaman, 2010).

The study identified key competencies leaders should possess to effectively develop high-potential academics, including cooperation, communication skills and expertise in performance management. These findings align with literature emphasising the significance of leadership qualities such as communication and mentoring in talent development (Fulmer et al., 2009). Effective leadership is crucial for nurturing talent and creating a supportive environment conducive to academic growth and innovation (Miller, 2014).

Participants highlighted various mechanisms, including work support, financial incentives, and conducive work environments, to maintain the happiness of high-potential academics. These findings are consistent with existing research emphasising the importance of effective leadership and supportive environments in employee satisfaction (Alfes et al., 2013; Gupta & Tayal, 2013). Leadership plays a critical role in fostering a positive work culture that promotes employee well-being and productivity (Lee et al., 2011).

Participants identified resource constraints, inadequate communication, and lack of talent management capacity, hindering leaders' efforts to develop high-potential academics. These findings align with literature highlighting the importance of adequate resources and supportive structures in talent development (Davin & Leal-Filho, 2015; Fulmer et al., 2009). Addressing these constraints requires strategic leadership and organisational support to create an environment conducive to talent development.

Participants emphasised the importance of measures such as competent leadership, project funding, and recognition to support the development of high-potential academics. These findings resonate with research emphasizing the significance of career management, funding, and leadership support in talent development (Hitka et al., 2012; Groysberg et al., 2004). Effective talent leadership involves creating opportunities for growth and recognition to nurture talent and drive organisational success.

Comprehensive Analysis and Recommendations

The findings from face-to-face interviews with participants offer insights into the identification and competencies of high-potential academics, the role of higher educational leaders in talent management and the competencies leaders should possess to develop them. High-potential academics were characterised by integrity and a commitment to student development, with competencies including knowledge and critical thinking. Leaders were found to play a crucial role in talent development and institutional success, requiring competencies in cooperation and communication.

Mechanisms to keep high-potential academics happy in the workplace, constraints on leaders, and recommendations for addressing challenges were also discussed, emphasising the importance of understanding employee needs and implementing effective talent management practices. Theoretical and empirical

recommendations were provided for Human Resource Management to improve talent management practices, while academics were encouraged to communicate grievances and suggestions for organisational improvement. Future research is recommended further to explore talent management and leadership practices in different provinces, aiming to enhance strategies for retaining high-potential academics and fostering institutional success.

Conclusion

Retaining high-potential academics in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) is crucial for delivering quality education and maintaining leadership. This study explored the role of talent management in developing these academics, finding that selecting suitable candidates and providing a supportive environment is key. Essential factors include motivation, satisfaction, and balancing input with rewards.

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